

Advanced Euler-Maclaurin-Type Inequalities via Tempered Fractional Integrals: A Focus on Functions of Bounded Variation

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Article Info

Oral Presentation

Doi: 10.5281/zenodo.14285548

Keywords

Inequalities of Maclaurin
 Fractional version
 Tempered fractional integrals
 Bounded function

Abstract

This research extends the seminal work of Hezenci and Budak [16] by developing advanced Euler Maclaurin-type inequalities using tempered fractional integrals. By utilizing a key lemma on tempered fractional integrals, we derive innovative inequalities for functions of bounded variation. These findings not only extend existing inequalities but also provide a more comprehensive framework for tempered fractional calculus. Furthermore, we examine specific cases to highlight the practical applications of these inequalities in numerical analysis and other fields.

1. Introduction and Preliminaries

Integral inequalities represent a modern approach in approximation theory, describing the growth rates in competing branches of mathematical analysis. In mathematical analysis, convex functions are vital for investigating inequalities due to their unique geometric and analytical traits. This model is also utilized in various fields, including ordinary differential equations [17, 31] and fractional calculus [19, 20].

Fractional calculus generalizes the notions of integrals and derivatives to non-integer orders, making it a powerful tool for modeling processes characterized by memory effects and anomalous diffusion. In this field, integral inequalities are fundamental for understanding how solutions to fractional differential equations behave, as these equations often include integrals and derivatives of arbitrary orders. Fractional inequalities, especially those connected to Jensen, Hermite-Hadamard, Simpson, and Euler-Maclaurin-type represent an important and varied field in mathematical analysis [3, 12, 21]. These inequalities provide key insights into the relationships governed by fractional calculus, aiding in a more refined understanding of functions and their integral behaviors.

Definition 1 (See [10]). Let $f \in L_1[a, b]$, the Riemann-Liouville fractional integral of order $\alpha > 0$, define as follows:

$$J_{a+}^{\alpha} f(x) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_a^x (x - \kappa)^{\alpha-1} f(\kappa) d\kappa, \quad x > a$$

and

$$J_{b-}^{\alpha} f(x) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_x^b (\kappa - x)^{\alpha-1} f(\kappa) d\kappa, \quad x < b.$$

Here, $\Gamma(\alpha)$ is the Gamma function and $J_{a+}^0 f(x) = J_{b-}^0 f(x) = f(x)$. For additional information on Riemann-Liouville fractional integrals, please refer to sources [11, 22, 27].

Simpson's rules are widely used in numerical analysis to approximate definite integrals and perform numerical integration. One of the most notable rules is Simpson's second-type rule, also known as Simpson's 3/8 rule, which provides a significant estimation frequently referenced in the literature.

Theorem 1. Consider that $f: [a, b] \rightarrow R$ is a four times continuously differentiable function on (a, b) , and $|f^{(4)}|_{\infty} = \sup_{x \in (a,b)} |f^{(4)}(x)| < \infty$. Then, the subsequent inequality holds:

$$\left| \frac{1}{8} \left[f(a) + 3f\left(\frac{2a+b}{3}\right) + 3f\left(\frac{a+2b}{3}\right) + f(b) \right] - \frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b f(x) dx \right| \leq \frac{1}{6480} |f^{(4)}|_{\infty} (b-a)^4.$$

This result is commonly known as a Newton-type inequality in the literature. Researchers have shown considerable interest in Simpson and Newton-type inequalities because of their extensive applications in applied mathematics. Many authors have introduced new Newton-type inequalities utilizing three-step quadratic kernels for different classes of functions. Alomari et al. [2] presented several Simpson-type

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inequalities for s-convex functions. Dragomir explored functions of bounded variation within the framework of the trapezoidal formula [7]. For more information on inequalities of this nature, readers are directed to [23, 26] and the references cited within them.

The Maclaurin rule, which serves as the dual form of Simpson’s 3/8 formula and is derived from the Maclaurin inequality, systematically estimates integrals. Maclaurin inequality is defined as follows:

Theorem 2. Consider that $f: [a, b] \rightarrow R$ is a four times continuously differentiable function on (a, b) , and $|f^{(4)}|_{\infty} = \sup_{\chi \in (a,b)} |f^{(4)}(\chi)| < \infty$. Then, the subsequent inequality valid:

$$\left| \frac{1}{8} \left[3f\left(\frac{5a+b}{6}\right) + 2f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + 3f\left(\frac{a+5b}{6}\right) \right] - \frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b f(\chi) d\chi \right| \leq \frac{7}{51840} |f^{(4)}|_{\infty} (b-a)^4.$$

Dedic et al. [8] established several inequalities for functions whose derivatives are either of bounded variation, Lipschitzian or belong to L^p -spaces by applying the Euler-Maclaurin formulas. These findings are subsequently used to derive error estimates for the Maclaurin quadrature rules. In [14], Euler-Maclaurin-type inequalities are derived for differentiable convex functions, utilizing Riemann-Liouville fractional integrals. For further insights into these types of inequalities, readers should look at [9, 25, 29].

Tempered fractional calculus is a generalization of fractional calculus, enabling the treatment of functions that exhibit growth at infinity while maintaining analytical control. In [4], Buschman was the first to define fractional integration using exponential kernels and weak singularities. Such inequalities provide sharper estimates for solutions of fractional differential equations, improving our understanding of physical systems that exhibit non-local behavior or memory effects. The following overview presents the essential preliminaries necessary to establish our main results.

Definition 2 (See [20]). For the real numbers $\alpha > 0$ and $\kappa, \lambda \geq 0$, the λ -incomplete gamma function described as:

$$\Upsilon_{\lambda}(\alpha, \kappa) := \int_0^{\kappa} \kappa^{\alpha-1} e^{-\lambda \kappa} d\kappa.$$

If $\lambda = 1$, it is equivalent to the incomplete gamma function [6]:

$$\Upsilon(\alpha, \kappa) := \int_0^{\kappa} \kappa^{\alpha-1} e^{-\kappa} d\kappa.$$

Here, $0 < \alpha < \infty$ and $\lambda \geq 0$.

Remark 1 (See [20]). For the real numbers $\alpha > 0$ and $\kappa, \lambda \geq 0$, we attain

- $\Upsilon_{\lambda(b-a)}(\alpha, 1) = \int_0^1 \kappa^{\alpha-1} e^{-\lambda(b-a)\kappa} d\kappa = \frac{1}{(b-a)^{\alpha}} \Upsilon_{\lambda}(\alpha, b-a)$,
- $\int_0^1 \Upsilon_{\lambda(b-a)}(\alpha, \kappa) d\kappa = \frac{\Upsilon_{\lambda}(\alpha, b-a)}{(b-a)^{\alpha}} - \frac{\Upsilon_{\lambda}(\alpha+1, b-a)}{(b-a)^{\alpha+1}}$.

Definition 3 (See [18, 22]). Tempered fractional integral operators of order $\alpha > 0$ and $\lambda \geq 0$ are presented as follows:

$$\mathcal{J}_{a+}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} f(\kappa) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_a^{\kappa} (\kappa - \kappa)^{\alpha-1} e^{-\lambda(\kappa-\kappa)} f(\kappa) d\kappa, \quad \kappa \in [a, b]$$

and

$$\mathcal{J}_{b-}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} f(\kappa) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_{\kappa}^b (\kappa - \kappa)^{\alpha-1} e^{-\lambda(\kappa-\kappa)} f(\kappa) d\kappa, \quad \kappa \in [a, b],$$

respectively for $f \in L_1[a, b]$.

If we assume $\lambda = 0$ results in the fractional integrals in Definition 3 being equivalent to the Riemann–Liouville fractional integral expressions in Definition 1. Almongeef et al. [1] have obtained Simpson-type inequalities for convex functions using tempered fractional integral operators. Haider et al. [13] established a key identity for differentiable functions in tempered fractional integrals, leading to modifications of fractional Milne inequalities. They introduced new expansions targeting convex functions, Lipschitzian functions, and functions of bounded variation. Several alternative formulations for tempered fractional integration are available in the literature, as discussed in the references found in books [5, 24, 27, 28, 30] and their associated sources.

In the context of tempered fractional integrals, Hezenci and Budak [16] have generalized Euler-Maclaurin-type inequalities for differentiable convex functions. Additionally, they utilized special cases of the derived theorems to explain their findings.

Lemma 1 (See [16]). Suppose $f: [a, b] \rightarrow R$ is an absolutely continuous function on the interval (a, b) with $f' \in L_1[a, b]$. Then the following Euler-Maclaurin-type equality is specifically tailored for tempered fractional integral is valid:

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{1}{8} \left[3f\left(\frac{5a+b}{6}\right) + 2f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + 3f\left(\frac{a+5b}{6}\right) \right] - \\ & \frac{\Gamma(\alpha)}{2\Upsilon_{\lambda}(\alpha, b-a)} \left[\mathfrak{J}_{b-}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} f(a) + \mathfrak{J}_{a+}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} f(b) \right] \\ & = \frac{(b-a)^{\alpha+1}}{2\Upsilon_{\lambda}(\alpha, b-a)} \left[\int_0^{\frac{1}{6}} (\Upsilon_{\lambda(b-a)}(\alpha, t)) [f'(tb + (1-t)a) - f'(ta + (1-t)b)] dt \right. \\ & + \int_{\frac{1}{6}}^{\frac{1}{2}} \left(\Upsilon_{\lambda(b-a)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{3}{8} \Upsilon_{\lambda(b-a)}(\alpha, 1) \right) [f'(t\rho + (1-t)a) - f'(ta + (1-t)b)] dt \\ & + \int_{\frac{1}{2}}^{\frac{5}{6}} \left(\Upsilon_{\lambda(b-a)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{5}{8} \Upsilon_{\lambda(b-a)}(\alpha, 1) \right) [f'(tb + (1-t)a) - f'(ta + (1-t)b)] dt \\ & \left. + \int_{\frac{5}{6}}^1 \left(\Upsilon_{\lambda(b-a)}(\alpha, t) - \Upsilon_{\lambda(b-a)}(\alpha, 1) \right) [f'(tb + (1-t)a) - f'(ta + (1-t)b)] dt \right]. \end{aligned}$$

Inspired by ongoing investigations, we extend new Euler-Maclaurin-type inequalities for functions of bounded variation using tempered fractional integrals, as guided by Lemma 1. The study begins with an introduction and

preliminaries, where we define key concepts in fractional calculus and review pertinent research. Then, we present Euler-Maclaurin-type inequalities for differentiable convex functions utilizing tempered fractional integrals, followed by examples that illustrate these inequalities and highlight their practical applications and importance. Finally, we discuss the implications of Euler-Maclaurin inequalities for future research directions.

Main Results

This section provides Euler-Maclaurin inequalities for functions of bounded variation by leveraging tempered fractional integrals.

Theorem 3. Consider a function $f: [a, b] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ exhibiting bounded variation over the interval $[a, b]$. Then, the following Euler-Maclaurin inequality is specifically formulated for tempered fractional integrals is valid:

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \frac{1}{8} \left[3f\left(\frac{5a+b}{6}\right) + 2f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + 3f\left(\frac{a+5b}{6}\right) \right] - \frac{\Gamma(\alpha)}{2\gamma_\lambda(\alpha, b-a)} \left[\mathcal{J}_{b^-}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} f(a) + \mathcal{J}_{a^+}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} f(b) \right] \right| \\ & \leq \frac{1}{\gamma_\lambda(\alpha, b-a)} \left[\max \left\{ \left| \gamma_\lambda\left(\alpha, \frac{b-a}{6}\right), \left| \gamma_\lambda\left(\alpha, \frac{b-a}{2}\right) - \frac{3\gamma_\lambda(\alpha, b-a)}{8} \right|, \left| \gamma_\lambda\left(\alpha, \frac{b-a}{2}\right) - \frac{3\gamma_\lambda(\alpha, b-a)}{8} \right|, \right. \right. \\ & \left. \left| \frac{5\gamma_\lambda(\alpha, b-a)}{8} - \gamma_\lambda\left(\alpha, \frac{5(b-a)}{6}\right) \right|, \left| \gamma_\lambda\left(\alpha, \frac{b-a}{2}\right) - \frac{5\gamma_\lambda(\alpha, b-a)}{8} \right|, \left| \gamma_\lambda\left(\alpha, \frac{5(b-a)}{6}\right) - \gamma_\lambda(\alpha, b-a) \right| \right\} \right] \bigvee_a^b(f). \end{aligned}$$

Here, $\bigvee_a^b(f)$ indicate the total variation of f on $[a, b]$.

Proof. Define the mappings

$$P_\alpha(\chi) = \begin{cases} \gamma_\lambda(\alpha, \chi - a), & a \leq \chi \leq \frac{5a+b}{6}, \\ \gamma_\lambda(\alpha, \chi - a) - \frac{3\gamma_\lambda(\alpha, b-a)}{8}, & \frac{5a+b}{6} \leq \chi \leq \frac{a+b}{2}, \\ \gamma_\lambda(\alpha, \chi - a) - \frac{5\gamma_\lambda(\alpha, b-a)}{8}, & \frac{a+b}{2} \leq \chi \leq \frac{a+5b}{6}, \\ \gamma_\lambda(\alpha, \chi - a) - \gamma_\lambda(\alpha, b-a), & \frac{a+5b}{6} \leq \chi \leq b, \end{cases}$$

and

$$R_\alpha(\chi) = \begin{cases} \gamma_\lambda(\alpha, b-a) - \gamma_\lambda(\alpha, b-\chi), & a \leq \chi \leq \frac{5a+b}{6}, \\ \frac{5\gamma_\lambda(\alpha, b-a)}{8} - \gamma_\lambda(\alpha, b-\chi), & \frac{5a+b}{6} \leq \chi \leq \frac{a+b}{2}, \\ \frac{3\gamma_\lambda(\alpha, b-a)}{8} - \gamma_\lambda(\alpha, b-\chi), & \frac{a+b}{2} \leq \chi \leq \frac{a+5b}{6}, \\ \gamma_\lambda(\alpha, b-\chi), & \frac{a+5b}{6} \leq \chi \leq b. \end{cases}$$

By implementing integration by parts, we acquire

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_a^b P_\alpha(\chi) df(\chi) \\ & = \int_a^{\frac{5a+b}{6}} \gamma_\lambda(\alpha, \chi - a) df(\chi) + \int_{\frac{5a+b}{6}}^{\frac{a+b}{2}} \left(\gamma_\lambda(\alpha, \chi - a) - \frac{3\gamma_\lambda(\alpha, b-a)}{8} \right) df(\chi) + \int_{\frac{a+b}{2}}^{\frac{a+5b}{6}} \left(\gamma_\lambda(\alpha, \chi - a) - \frac{5\gamma_\lambda(\alpha, b-a)}{8} \right) df(\chi) + \int_{\frac{a+5b}{6}}^b \left(\gamma_\lambda(\alpha, \chi - a) - \gamma_\lambda(\alpha, b-a) \right) df(\chi) \\ & = \gamma_\lambda(\alpha, \chi - a) f(\chi) \Big|_a^{\frac{5a+b}{6}} - \int_a^{\frac{5a+b}{6}} (\chi - a)^{\alpha-1} e^{-\lambda(\chi-a)} f(\chi) d\chi \\ & \quad + \left(\gamma_\lambda(\alpha, \chi - a) - \frac{3\gamma_\lambda(\alpha, b-a)}{8} \right) f(\chi) \Big|_{\frac{5a+b}{6}}^{\frac{a+b}{2}} - \int_{\frac{5a+b}{6}}^{\frac{a+b}{2}} (\chi - a)^{\alpha-1} e^{-\lambda(\chi-a)} f(\chi) d\chi \\ & \quad + \left(\gamma_\lambda(\alpha, \chi - a) - \frac{5\gamma_\lambda(\alpha, b-a)}{8} \right) f(\chi) \Big|_{\frac{a+b}{2}}^{\frac{a+5b}{6}} - \int_{\frac{a+b}{2}}^{\frac{a+5b}{6}} (\chi - a)^{\alpha-1} e^{-\lambda(\chi-a)} f(\chi) d\chi \\ & \quad + (\gamma_\lambda(\alpha, \chi - a) - \gamma_\lambda(\alpha, b-a)) f(\chi) \Big|_{\frac{a+5b}{6}}^b - \int_{\frac{a+5b}{6}}^b (\chi - a)^{\alpha-1} e^{-\lambda(\chi-a)} f(\chi) d\chi \\ & = \frac{3\gamma_\lambda(\alpha, b-a)}{8} f\left(\frac{5a+b}{6}\right) + \frac{2\gamma_\lambda(\alpha, b-a)}{8} f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + \frac{5\gamma_\lambda(\alpha, b-a)}{8} f\left(\frac{a+5b}{6}\right) - \Gamma(\alpha) \mathcal{J}_{b^-}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} f(a) \\ & = \frac{\gamma_\lambda(\alpha, b-a)}{8} \left[3f\left(\frac{5a+b}{6}\right) + 2f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + 3f\left(\frac{a+5b}{6}\right) \right] - \Gamma(\alpha) \mathcal{J}_{b^-}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} f(a) \end{aligned}$$

Likewise, we obtain

$$R_\alpha(\chi) = \frac{\gamma_\lambda(\alpha, b-a)}{8} \left[3f\left(\frac{5a+b}{6}\right) + 2f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + 3f\left(\frac{a+5b}{6}\right) \right] - \Gamma(\alpha) \mathcal{J}_{a^+}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} f(b).$$

Hence, we acquire

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{1}{8} \left[3f\left(\frac{5a+b}{6}\right) + 2f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + 3f\left(\frac{a+5b}{6}\right) \right] - \frac{\Gamma(\alpha)}{2\gamma_\lambda(\alpha, b-a)} \left[\mathcal{J}_{b^-}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} f(a) + \mathcal{J}_{a^+}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} f(b) \right] \\ & = \frac{1}{2\gamma_\lambda(\alpha, b-a)} \int_a^b [P_\alpha(\chi) + R_\alpha(\chi)] df(\chi). \end{aligned}$$

It is a well-established fact that if functions g and f are defined on the interval $[a, b]$, where g is continuous on $[a, b]$ and f has bounded variation on the same interval, then the integral $\int_a^b g(\kappa) df(\kappa)$ exists and

$$\left| \int_a^b g(\kappa) df(\kappa) \right| \leq \sup_{\kappa \in [a, b]} |g(\kappa)| \bigvee_a^b(f). \tag{1}$$

On a different note, the use of (1) reveals

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \left| \frac{1}{8} \left[3f\left(\frac{5a+b}{6}\right) + 2f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + 3f\left(\frac{a+5b}{6}\right) \right] \right. \\
 & \quad \left. - \frac{\Gamma(\alpha)}{2Y_\lambda(\alpha, b-a)} \left[J_{b^-}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} f(a) + J_{a^+}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} f(b) \right] \right| \\
 = & \frac{1}{2Y_\lambda(\alpha, b-a)} \left[\left| \int_a^b \mathcal{P}_\alpha(\chi) df(\chi) \right| + \left| \int_a^b \mathcal{R}_\alpha(\chi) df(\chi) \right| \right] \\
 \leq & \frac{1}{2Y_\lambda(\alpha, b-a)} \left[\left| \int_a^{\frac{5a+b}{6}} Y_\lambda(\alpha, \chi-a) df(\chi) \right| \right. \\
 & \quad \left. + \left| \int_{\frac{5a+b}{6}}^{\frac{a+b}{2}} \left(Y_\lambda(\alpha, \chi-a) - \frac{3Y_\lambda(\alpha, b-a)}{8} \right) df(\chi) \right| \right. \\
 & \quad \left. + \left| \int_{\frac{a+b}{2}}^{\frac{a+5b}{6}} \left(Y_\lambda(\alpha, \chi-a) - \frac{5Y_\lambda(\alpha, b-a)}{8} \right) df(\chi) \right| \right. \\
 & \quad \left. + \left| \int_{\frac{a+5b}{6}}^b (Y_\lambda(\alpha, \chi-a) - Y_\lambda(\alpha, b-a)) df(\chi) \right| \right. \\
 & \quad \left. + \left| \int_a^{\frac{5a+b}{6}} (Y_\lambda(\alpha, b-a) - Y_\lambda(\alpha, b-\chi)) df(\chi) \right| \right. \\
 & \quad \left. + \left| \int_{\frac{5a+b}{6}}^{\frac{a+b}{2}} \left(\frac{5Y_\lambda(\alpha, b-a)}{8} - Y_\lambda(\alpha, b-\chi) \right) df(\chi) \right| \right. \\
 & \quad \left. + \left| \int_{\frac{a+b}{2}}^{\frac{a+5b}{6}} \left(\frac{3Y_\lambda(\alpha, b-a)}{8} - Y_\lambda(\alpha, b-\chi) \right) df(\chi) \right| \right. \\
 & \quad \left. + \left| \int_{\frac{a+5b}{6}}^b Y_\lambda(\alpha, b-\chi) df(\chi) \right| \right] \\
 \leq & \frac{1}{2Y_\lambda(\alpha, b-a)} \left[\sup_{\chi \in \left[a, \frac{5a+b}{6} \right]} |Y_\lambda(\alpha, \chi-a)| \frac{\frac{5a+b}{6}}{a} (f) \right. \\
 & \quad \left. + \sup_{\chi \in \left[\frac{5a+b}{6}, \frac{a+b}{2} \right]} |Y_\lambda(\alpha, \chi-a) - \frac{3Y_\lambda(\alpha, b-a)}{8}| \frac{\frac{a+b}{2}}{\frac{5a+b}{6}} (f) \right. \\
 & \quad \left. - \frac{3Y_\lambda(\alpha, b-a)}{8} \right] \frac{\frac{a+b}{2}}{\frac{5a+b}{6}} (f) \\
 & \quad \left. + \sup_{\chi \in \left[\frac{a+b}{2}, \frac{a+5b}{6} \right]} |Y_\lambda(\alpha, \chi-a) - \frac{5Y_\lambda(\alpha, b-a)}{8}| \frac{\frac{a+b}{2}}{\frac{a+b}{2}} (f) \right. \\
 & \quad \left. + \sup_{\chi \in \left[\frac{a+5b}{6}, b \right]} |Y_\lambda(\alpha, \chi-a) - Y_\lambda(\alpha, b-a)| \frac{\frac{5a+b}{6}}{a} (f) \right]
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & + \sup_{\chi \in \left[\frac{a+b}{2}, \frac{a+5b}{6} \right]} \left| Y_\lambda(\alpha, \chi-a) - \frac{5Y_\lambda(\alpha, b-a)}{8} \right| \frac{\frac{a+b}{2}}{\frac{a+b}{2}} (f) \\
 & \quad + \sup_{\chi \in \left[\frac{a+5b}{6}, b \right]} |Y_\lambda(\alpha, \chi-a) - Y_\lambda(\alpha, b-a)| \frac{\frac{5a+b}{6}}{a} (f) \\
 & \quad - a) \left| \frac{\frac{a+b}{2}}{\frac{5a+b}{6}} (f) \right. \\
 & \quad \left. + \sup_{\chi \in \left[a, \frac{5a+b}{6} \right]} |Y_\lambda(\alpha, b-\chi) - Y_\lambda(\alpha, b-a)| \frac{\frac{5a+b}{6}}{a} (f) \right. \\
 & \quad \left. + \sup_{\chi \in \left[\frac{5a+b}{6}, \frac{a+b}{2} \right]} \left| \frac{5Y_\lambda(\alpha, b-a)}{8} - Y_\lambda(\alpha, b-\chi) \right| \frac{\frac{a+b}{2}}{\frac{5a+b}{6}} (f) \right. \\
 & \quad \left. + \sup_{\chi \in \left[\frac{a+b}{2}, \frac{a+5b}{6} \right]} \left| \frac{3Y_\lambda(\alpha, b-a)}{8} - Y_\lambda(\alpha, b-\chi) \right| \frac{\frac{a+b}{2}}{\frac{a+b}{2}} (f) \right. \\
 & \quad \left. + \sup_{\chi \in \left[\frac{a+5b}{6}, b \right]} |Y_\lambda(\alpha, b-\chi)| \frac{\frac{5a+b}{6}}{\frac{a+b}{2}} (f) \right] \\
 = & \frac{1}{2Y_\lambda(\alpha, b-a)} \left[Y_\lambda\left(\alpha, \frac{b-a}{6}\right) \frac{\frac{5a+b}{6}}{a} (f) \right. \\
 & \quad \left. + \max \left\{ \left| Y_\lambda\left(\alpha, \frac{b-a}{6}\right) - \frac{3Y_\lambda(\alpha, b-a)}{8} \right|, \left| Y_\lambda\left(\alpha, \frac{b-a}{2}\right) - \frac{3Y_\lambda(\alpha, b-a)}{8} \right| \right\} \frac{\frac{a+b}{2}}{\frac{5a+b}{6}} (f) \right. \\
 & \quad \left. + \max \left\{ \left| Y_\lambda\left(\alpha, \frac{b-a}{2}\right) - \frac{5Y_\lambda(\alpha, b-a)}{8} \right|, \left| Y_\lambda\left(\alpha, \frac{5(b-a)}{6}\right) - \frac{5Y_\lambda(\alpha, b-a)}{8} \right| \right\} \frac{\frac{a+b}{2}}{\frac{a+b}{2}} (f) \right. \\
 & \quad \left. + \left| Y_\lambda\left(\alpha, \frac{5(b-a)}{6}\right) - Y_\lambda(\alpha, b-a) \right| \frac{\frac{5a+b}{6}}{\frac{a+b}{2}} (f) \right. \\
 & \quad \left. + \left| Y_\lambda\left(\alpha, \frac{5(b-a)}{6}\right) - Y_\lambda\left(\alpha, \frac{5(b-a)}{6}\right) - Y_\lambda(\alpha, b-a) \right| \frac{\frac{5a+b}{6}}{a} (f) \right. \\
 & \quad \left. + \max \left\{ \left| \frac{5Y_\lambda(\alpha, b-a)}{8} - Y_\lambda\left(\alpha, \frac{5(b-a)}{6}\right) \right|, \left| \frac{5Y_\lambda(\alpha, b-a)}{8} - Y_\lambda\left(\alpha, \frac{b-a}{2}\right) \right| \right\} \frac{\frac{a+b}{2}}{\frac{5a+b}{6}} (f) \right. \\
 & \quad \left. + \max \left\{ \left| \frac{3Y_\lambda(\alpha, b-a)}{8} - Y_\lambda\left(\alpha, \frac{b-a}{2}\right) \right|, \left| \frac{3Y_\lambda(\alpha, b-a)}{8} - Y_\lambda\left(\alpha, \frac{b-a}{6}\right) \right| \right\} \frac{\frac{a+b}{2}}{\frac{5a+b}{6}} (f) \right. \\
 & \quad \left. + Y_\lambda\left(\alpha, \frac{b-a}{6}\right) \frac{\frac{5a+b}{6}}{a} (f) \right]
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= \frac{1}{\Upsilon_\lambda(\alpha, b-a)} \left[\max \left\{ \Upsilon_\lambda \left(\alpha, \frac{b-a}{6} \right), \left| \Upsilon_\lambda \left(\alpha, \frac{b-a}{6} \right) - \frac{3\Upsilon_\lambda(\alpha, b-a)}{8} \right|, \left| \Upsilon_\lambda \left(\alpha, \frac{b-a}{2} \right) - \frac{3\Upsilon_\lambda(\alpha, b-a)}{8} \right|, \right. \\
 &\left. \left| \frac{5\Upsilon_\lambda(\alpha, b-a)}{8} - \Upsilon_\lambda \left(\alpha, \frac{5(b-a)}{6} \right) \right|, \left| \Upsilon_\lambda \left(\alpha, \frac{b-a}{2} \right) - \frac{5\Upsilon_\lambda(\alpha, b-a)}{8} \right|, \right. \\
 &\left. \left| \Upsilon_\lambda \left(\alpha, \frac{5(b-a)}{6} \right) - \Upsilon_\lambda(\alpha, b-a) \right| \right] \frac{b}{a} \vee (f).
 \end{aligned}$$

Thus, the proof is accomplished.

Corollary 1. If we stipulate that $\lambda = 0$ in Theorem 3, we come across

$$\begin{aligned}
 &\left| \frac{1}{8} \left[3f \left(\frac{5a+b}{6} \right) + 2f \left(\frac{a+b}{2} \right) + 3f \left(\frac{a+5b}{6} \right) \right] - \frac{\Gamma(\alpha+1)}{2(b-a)^\alpha} \left[J_{b^-}^{(\alpha,\lambda)} f(a) + J_{a^+}^{(\alpha,\lambda)} f(b) \right] \right| \\
 &\leq \max \left\{ \frac{1}{6^\alpha}, \left| \frac{1}{6^\alpha} - \frac{3}{8} \right|, \left| \frac{1}{2^\alpha} - \frac{3}{8} \right|, \left| \left(\frac{5}{6} \right)^\alpha - \frac{5}{8} \right|, \left| \frac{1}{2^\alpha} - \frac{5}{8} \right|, \left(1 - \left(\frac{5}{6} \right)^\alpha \right) \right\}
 \end{aligned}$$

Remark 2. Assume $\lambda = 0$ and $\alpha = 1$ in Theorem 3, it becomes

$$\left| \frac{1}{8} \left[3f \left(\frac{5a+b}{6} \right) + 2f \left(\frac{a+b}{2} \right) + 3f \left(\frac{a+5b}{6} \right) \right] - \frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b f(x) dx \right| \leq \frac{5}{24} \vee_a^b(f), \text{ which is covered in [12].}$$

Conclusion

The development of Euler-Maclaurin-type inequalities marks a major step forward in mathematical analysis, building on the foundational work of Hezenci and Budak [16] through the application of tempered fractional integrals. By employing a key Lemma 1 on tempered fractional integrals, we derive innovative inequalities for functions of bounded variation. These findings not only expand upon existing inequalities but also offer a more comprehensive framework for tempered fractional calculus. Overall, this research enriches the landscape of mathematical analysis and provides valuable insights for future research.

Declaration of Ethical Standards

The author(s) of this article declare that the materials and methods used in this study do not require ethical committee permission and/or legal-special permission.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have

appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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